

THE IMPORTANCE OF MOVEMENT GAMES IN DEVELOPING PHYSICAL QUALITIES OF ATHLETES

Alimov Jamshid Artiqovich

Andijan State Pedagogical Institute, Associate Professor of the Department of Physical Education and Women's Sports.

Akhmadjonov Muhammadyusuf Rahmatullo ogli

Master's Student at Andijan State Pedagogical Institute,

+998-90-623-19-54 Muhammadyusufahmadjonov959@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14911504>

Abstract. *This article discusses the theoretical considerations specific to movement games in wrestling and how they determine the potential of physical education and sports. It emphasizes the unparalleled importance of movement games, including national games, in the training of wrestlers. It is well known that the development of physical qualities is a vital tool for athletes, which is why coaches pay special attention to enhancing athletes' physical attributes. Athletes with well-developed physical qualities tend to have greater capabilities.*

Keywords: *wrestling, youth sports, athletes, wrestling history.*

ВАЖНОСТЬ ПОДВИЖНЫХ ИГР В РАЗВИТИИ ФИЗИЧЕСКИХ КАЧЕСТВ СПОРТСМЕНОВ

Аннотация. *В этой статье обсуждаются теоретические соображения, характерные для подвижных игр в борьбе, и то, как они определяют потенциал физического воспитания и спорта. Подчеркивается непревзойденная важность подвижных игр, включая национальные игры, в подготовке борцов. Хорошо известно, что развитие физических качеств является жизненно важным инструментом для спортсменов, поэтому тренеры уделяют особое внимание улучшению физических характеристик спортсменов. Спортсмены с хорошо развитыми физическими качествами, как правило, обладают большими возможностями.*

Ключевые слова: *борьба, молодежный спорт, спортсмены, история борьбы.*

A society that prioritizes sports develops as a healthy and progressive community. Various types of sports contribute not only to the physical well-being of individuals but also to their spiritual development. In particular, wrestling serves as a protector of national values, fostering a sense of national pride, honor, and confidence in a bright future. The art of wrestling has been known to many nations since ancient times. This sport involves a one-on-one competition between two athletes according to established rules. Wrestling was widely practiced in ancient Greece and became a regular part of the ancient Olympic Games.

Today, different forms of wrestling are popular in countries such as Greece, Italy, Japan, Turkey, Iran, Afghanistan, Russia, Uzbekistan, Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, and many others. [1]

In today's sports practice, there is a growing need for a fresh approach to training talented young wrestlers. This necessity is particularly driven by the need to effectively develop the physical fitness of young wrestlers and integrate new teaching methodologies and innovative technologies into wrestling training sessions. Physical preparation plays a crucial role in developing highly skilled young wrestlers and serves as a foundation for other types of training.

The better developed the physical qualities of wrestlers, the more proficient they become in mastering wrestling techniques. Numerous scholars and experienced coaches emphasize that using movement games in the development of wrestlers' physical abilities yields highly effective results. Movement games, including traditional folk games, are considered one of the main tools for enhancing physical qualities.

A literary analysis of the aforementioned and other sources reveals that while attention has been paid to the methods and techniques of using movement games alongside other tools for developing wrestlers' physical qualities, there is a noticeable lack of information regarding the classification of games when applied to young wrestlers. In our view, this gap highlights the necessity of improving the process of using movement games for the physical development of young wrestlers. Currently, one of the pressing tasks is to develop new technologies for incorporating movement games into training and to carefully select appropriate games for this purpose. [2]

Strength is considered one of the most essential qualities for athletes, and there are numerous effective elements for enhancing it. However, when strength is developed through movement games, training becomes both engaging and enjoyable. It is well known that movement games are diverse and highly beneficial. Examples include games such as "Hooked Legs", "The One Who Dodges Loses", and "Riders' Wrestling". [3]

Hooked Legs Game - Two wrestlers lie on the mat in opposite directions on their backs, holding each other's hands. When the whistle signal is given, they attempt to hook their opponent's legs using their left or right leg. The wrestlers strive to unbalance and overturn each other. The rule of the game states that the wrestler who first manages to lift their opponent off the mat is declared the winner.

The One Who Dodges Loses - Two wrestlers compete inside a 3-meter diameter circle.

They hold each other's waists with their arms crossed in an "X" position. Their task, after the whistle signal, is to lift their opponent's feet off the mat and push them out of the circle. The rules prohibit swinging the arms, twisting, or using the legs.

Hooked Feet Game - Wrestlers are divided into pairs and attempt to hook their opponent's leg using their own. After the whistle signal, they use strength to unbalance their opponent by hooking their feet. The rule of the game states that the wrestler who first loses balance and touches the mat with their foot is considered the loser. Holding the opponent by the shoulders is prohibited.

Exercises for developing speed exercises must be performed at maximum intensity to cultivate speed. Games that require quick responses to signals, multiple movements within a specific time frame, or fast spatial movements of the entire body or its parts help develop the quality of speed in learners. Special attention is given to games that encourage active competition between two groups. Games that train reaction to moving objects are particularly effective in this regard. Examples include "Protect the Handkerchief", "Tag the Ball", and "Little Turtles".

Protect the Handkerchief - A wrestler with a handkerchief tied around their waist stands in the center of a circle as the leader. Outside the circle are three other wrestlers. Each wrestler is allowed to take one step inside the circle. The goal of the central wrestler is to protect their handkerchief and prevent it from being taken.

If a wrestler manages to grab the handkerchief, they become the new leader, while the previous leader exits the game.

Rules:

- The leader must not step outside the circle.
- Other wrestlers are not allowed to place both feet inside the circle.

Tag the Ball - One wrestler inside the circle holds a ball. Their task is to tag their opponent's shoulder with the ball. The opponent, on the other hand, tries to avoid being tagged by moving and dodging within the circle.

Rules:

- The wrestler holding the ball must tag the opponent with it.
- If a wrestler steps outside the circle, they are considered the loser.

Little Turtles - This game is played on a soft carpeted field. Each wrestler has a handkerchief tucked into their belt. The objective is to crawl on all fours and try to grab the opponent's handkerchief.

Rules:

- The winner is determined by the number of handkerchiefs they successfully collect.
- Players who lose their handkerchief are eliminated from the game.

Games that develop agility typically require precise movements and adaptability to changing conditions. National games, where quick reactions and agility are essential, are particularly effective for developing this quality.

The Quickest - Wrestlers kneel in pairs. The objective is to touch the opponent's shoulder as many times as possible while preventing them from doing the same. The wrestler who successfully touches their opponent's shoulder more times is declared the winner.

Rule:

- Wrestlers must gently tap their opponent's shoulder.

Watch Your Feet = Wrestlers pair up and place their hands on each other's shoulders.

The task is to quickly and skillfully tap the opponent's feet with their own as many times as possible.

Rule:

- Wrestlers must avoid having their opponent's feet touch their own and must keep their hands on the shoulders without letting them drop.

Claps - A circle with a 3-meter diameter is drawn on the floor or field. Two wrestlers are selected, and their goal is to quickly and gently tap underneath the opponent's knees while avoiding being tapped themselves. The wrestler who taps more times wins.

Rule:

- Wrestlers are not allowed to grab each other's hands or step outside the circle.

Games for Developing Endurance Many traditional national movement games cultivate physical qualities such as speed and endurance due to the intense exercises they involve. In these games, physical load (intensity) is gradually increased using various methods, such as:

- Expanding the playing field
- Reducing the number of players without decreasing the field size
- Increasing the number of game tools (sticks, handkerchiefs, hats, coats, balls, etc.)
- Extending running distances
- Adding more obstacles
- Incorporating more complex exercises and increasing their frequency

When these methods are applied consistently, goals are achieved more efficiently.

Examples of such games include "Cart Race" and "Arm Wrestling".

Cart Race - One wrestler supports themselves on their hands while keeping their legs straight and shoulder-width apart. Their partner holds their legs, forming a structure called a "cart." The task is to touch the opponent's designated hand as many times as possible. The wrestler who loses balance first is considered defeated.

Rules:

- Wrestlers are not allowed to rest on their elbows or lie flat on their stomachs.

Arm Wrestling - Wrestlers face each other with their feet close together. They use their palms to push against each other, trying to disrupt the opponent's balance.

Rules:

- If a wrestler moves their feet during the palm push, they are considered defeated.

Developing Flexibility - Special attention should be given to enhancing wrestlers' flexibility since, as mentioned earlier, the development of flexibility slows over time. Games targeting specific muscle groups and joints are selected to improve this quality. These games are often conducted with the help of special sports equipment, although the participants themselves can sometimes serve as resistance instead of weights. Active flexibility is closely linked to muscle strength, while the stretching properties of muscles are influenced by the central nervous system. Therefore, when participants engage in these games with enthusiasm, flexibility improves more significantly. Before engaging in games that require flexibility, appropriate light physical exercises should be performed.

Examples of such games include:

-Attempting to Escape

-Triple Chase on the Field

-Heated Debate

Attempting to Escape - Wrestlers from the first team hold each other's hands to form a circle. Wrestlers from the second team remain inside the circle and attempt to escape by bending or kneeling as they try to break through the enclosure.

Game Rule:

-The team that manages to keep more wrestlers trapped inside the circle is declared the winner.[4]

Triangle Play - Two wrestlers stand face to face, while a third wrestler positions themselves opposite one of them. The task for the two players is to try to tag each other.

Meanwhile, the third wrestler stands in the center, bending and moving to obstruct them, preventing free movement.

Game Rule:

-Players are not allowed to step outside the marked boundary. The player who loses takes the position of the referee.

Intense Duel - Wrestlers stand back-to-back, firmly gripping a gymnastics stick raised high. Their task is to pull the stick toward themselves, forcing their opponent's feet off the ground or causing them to bend.

Game Rule:

- A player loses if their feet leave the ground or if they release the stick. The wrestler who lifts their opponent while remaining bent and holds them for five seconds is declared the winner.

Conclusion

The analysis of scientific and methodological literature demonstrates that the theoretical perspectives associated with movement games highlight their potential in physical education and sports. The importance of incorporating movement games, particularly national traditional games, in training young wrestlers is invaluable.

In recent years, significant attention has been devoted to improving the training phases and system approaches for wrestlers. Beyond regular training, the effectiveness of exercises aimed at developing movement skills and related physical qualities through movement games has been studied by leading experts in wrestling. These findings underscore the practical value of such games in enhancing athletic preparation and performance. [5]

In the preparation phase of wrestlers, special emphasis must be placed on developing their specific physical qualities, as this plays a crucial role in achieving high results in competitions.

During wrestler training, rational alternation of exercises based on the intensity and focus of the workload, as well as microcycles structured according to the program aligned with practical experience results, ensures enhanced special work capacity and significant improvement in competitive performance.

One of the primary approaches to developing physical qualities in wrestlers is the use of regulated exercises, which promote gradual and targeted physical development. This method helps athletes achieve peak performance levels while minimizing the risk of injury.

REFERENCES

1. A.X.Komilov “Kurash sporti uning shakillanish tarixi, o‘zbek kurash paydo bo‘lishi va qoidalari”, “Экономика и социум №2 (105) 2023 1- bet
2. S.R.Qodirov “Yosh kurashchilarni jismoniy sifatlarini rivojlantirishda harakatli o‘yinlardan samarali foydalanish” <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/yosh-kurashchilarni-jismoniy-sifatlarini-rivojlantirishda-harakatli-o-yinlardan-samarali-foydalanish/viewer>
3. F.A.Kerimov “Kurush elementlarga ega harakatli o‘yinlar” Toshkent 2020-yil
4. O‘zbekiston Milliy Ensiklopediyasi 2000-2005-yil
5. Glenn Kirchner, Graham J.Fishburne. Physical Education For elementary School Children. Brown and Benchmark. Madision. USA.1995.-620 p.